

DOENÇA DE ALZHEIMER:

estrutura intelectual da literatura científica da América Latina e Caribe

▪ PERÍODO – 1986-2004

BRASIL

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Alzheimer Dementia" OR "Alzheimer Dementias" OR "Dementia, Alzheimer" OR "Alzheimer's Diseases" OR "Dementia, Senile" OR "Senile Dementia" OR "Dementia, Alzheimer Type" OR "Alzheimer Type Dementia" OR "Alzheimer-Type Dementia (ATD)" OR "Alzheimer Type Dementia (ATD)" OR "Dementia, Alzheimer-Type (ATD)" OR "Alzheimer Type Senile Dementia" OR "Primary Senile Degenerative Dementia" OR "Dementia, Primary Senile Degenerative" OR "Alzheimer Sclerosis" OR "Sclerosis, Alzheimer" OR "Alzheimer Syndrome" OR "Alzheimer's Diseases" OR "Alzheimer Diseases" OR "Alzheimers Diseases" OR "Senile Dementia, Alzheimer Type" OR "Acute Confusional Senile Dementia" OR "Senile Dementia, Acute Confusional" OR "Dementia, Presenile" OR "Presenile Dementia" OR "Alzheimer Disease, Late Onset" OR "Late Onset Alzheimer Disease" OR "Alzheimer's Diseases, Focal Onset" OR "Focal Onset Alzheimer's Diseases" OR "Familial Alzheimer Disease (FAD)" OR "Alzheimer Disease, Familial (FAD)" OR "Familial Alzheimer Diseases (FAD)" OR "Alzheimer Disease, Early Onset" OR "Early Onset Alzheimer Disease" OR "Presenile Alzheimer Dementia" OR "Amyloid beta-Peptides" OR "Amyloid beta-Protein Precursor" OR "Cerebral Amyloid Angiopathy" OR "tau Proteins" OR "Neurofilament Proteins" OR "Kluver-Bucy Syndrome" OR "Neurocognitive Disorders" OR "Neurodegenerative Diseases" OR "Brain Diseases" OR dementia) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (brazil) AND PUBYEAR > 1985 AND PUBYEAR < 2005 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re"))

AMÉRICA LATINA E CARIBE

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OR Montserrat OR "Saint Lucia" OR "Saint Kitts and Nevis" OR Suriname OR "Trinidad and Tobago") AND PUBYEAR > 1985 AND PUBYEAR < 2005 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re"))

▪ **PERÍODO – 2005-2023**

BRASIL

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